

**“THE SIGNIFICANCE OF AN INDIVIDUAL'S
SPIRITUAL AND MORAL DEVELOPMENT AND THE
PRINCIPLES OF SOCIAL JUSTICE AS AN
IDEOLOGICAL FACTOR OF CIVIL SOCIETY.”**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the ideological significance of personal spiritual development and the principles of social justice in the formation of civil society. The role of a morally mature individual in the development of society, along with their ethical values, responsibility, and civic position, is interpreted as a key factor in ensuring the stable functioning of social institutions. The article also highlights the role of social justice principles in building a legal and democratic state, ensuring equal rights for citizens, and strengthening an atmosphere of trust within society. The study scientifically substantiates that a spiritually developed individual and a justice-based social system, in harmony with each other, constitute the ideological foundation of civil society.

The spiritual maturity of the individual is the basis of the spiritual, cultural and civic stability of every society. The basis of the ideas of social justice and equality ultimately goes back to the value of the human person. At the global level, regardless of the culture, the well-being of the state in all of them is associated with the appreciation and realization of the interests of people at the social level, in society. Spiritual maturity is a state of harmony in the inner world of a person of goodness, conscience, justice and responsibility, which allows him to distinguish himself from the animal world. In the words of Al-Farabi, “A person reaches happiness through knowledge and morality.” This idea shows the unity of the two foundations of human spirituality, science and morality. Therefore, spiritual maturity is manifested not only through knowledge, but also through internal moral consciousness.

Indeed, as the Greek philosopher Plato noted, a person cannot reach perfection in isolation from society, and it is society that serves as the main factor in the formation of his social consciousness, his self-awareness. His idea that “Justice is the conscientious performance of each person’s work” shows the responsibility of each individual in a civil society. For example, in Uzbekistan, through the “Prosperous Village” and “Prosperous Neighborhood” programs, each citizen contributes to the prosperity of his country, which is a practical expression of civic spirituality.

is interpreted as a person's struggle with the ego, moral purification, and approaching Allah through enlightenment. "A perfect person is one who combines intelligence and virtue

with the soul, not the body." That is, spiritual perfection is seen in a person's achievement of scientific and moral maturity. In it, spirituality complements science, morality, and public service and allows a person who has embarked on the path of self-realization to evaluate his own activities. In this sense, Ibn Sina's definition, "Unless a person educates his ego, the light of enlightenment will not shine in him," shows his connection of spiritual perfection with the process of inner purification and knowledge. Ahmed Yasawi **In the saying**, "He who conquers the self is spiritually perfect," spiritual perfection means victory over the self and spiritual purity. In Western philosophy, spiritual maturity is interpreted as a person's attainment of maturity through intellectual independence, freedom, and conscience. For example According to Immanuel Kant, "Spiritual perfection is the ability of a person to act according to his own mind and conscience," and according to him, spiritual perfection requires the understanding of moral laws not through external obligations, but through internal conscience. In Hegel's idea that "The spirit is free only when it understands itself," spiritual perfection represents the spirit's emergence into freedom in society through the process of self-understanding. It should be emphasized that, In modern philosophical dictionaries, in particular, in the dictionary of philosophy published in Russia, "Spiritual perfection is a state of internal perfection formed in the human mind through the harmony of goodness, conscience and moral ideals," according to which spirituality is interpreted as internal hygiene, that is, the mental health of a person. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, "Spiritual perfection is a state of a person's maturity in terms of intellect, morality and knowledge, and a sense of responsibility to society," 129 and in this definition, national spiritual perfection is associated with social responsibility According to the President of Uzbekistan, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev: "Spirituality is the harmony of conscience, morality and patriotism in the human soul," that is, spirituality is connected with the national idea and state values, that is, spiritual maturity is a high manifestation of civic responsibility. According to Academician IA Karimov "Spirituality is the soul of a nation, and perfection is its living movement," because spiritual perfection is the spiritual mobility of a nation, that is, the internal energy of development. In our opinion, the concept of spiritual perfection is associated with moral purification and enlightenment in Eastern philosophy, Sufism In the philosophy of the ancients, spiritual maturity is associated with overcoming the ego and spiritual elevation, and in Western philosophy it is interpreted with conscience, freedom and independent consciousness, while in modern philosophy and the national school, spiritual maturity is seen in harmony with social responsibility and patriotism. Therefore, spiritual maturity is a social manifestation of spiritual and moral maturity in a person's inner world.

In our opinion, these factors are related to the inner world, spiritual and moral state of a person. They are the main foundation of the spiritual perfection of a person, and they include the provision of a balance of conscience and morality, the pursuit of goodness, justice and truth by a person, the illumination of science and knowledge by a person's heart, the realization of one's own capabilities and duties through selfawareness and responsibility, the development of spiritual freedom and philosophical thinking in exchange for the provision of creative thought and independence. In this sense, Al-Farabi's idea that "The soul guided by reason leads to perfection" shows that the internal source of spiritual perfection is in the mind and conscience of a person.

In our opinion, the first school of spiritual formation is the family and educational institutions, which form moral, national and cultural values in a person. From this point of view, the family is an environment of love, decency and responsibility, school and university education is a harmony of science and spirituality, the teacher's personality is a spiritual example and source of inspiration, the content of education is a harmony of national values and universal ideas, which represent the role of civil society institutions in the formation of the spiritual maturity of a person. That is, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized: "The main task in the education system is to harmonize spirituality with science."

So, what is the importance of the role of the family in ensuring the spiritual development of the individual and the development of civil society in the present era? In the present era, the family is an important natural place where a person is born, lives, and makes a worthy contribution to the life of society, and the environment in it is the initial basis for personal development. From this perspective, the professional development of family members affects the worldview and determination of the life goals of the children living in it. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, in order to preserve families, special attention is paid to the issue of preparing young people for starting a family, and the Institute of Brides, reproductive health centers, etc., provide recommendations to young brides on preserving the family.

It should be noted that in world experience, special attention is paid to the harmony of spirituality and justice. For example, Martin Luther King's 1963 speech "I Have a Dream" in which he said, "Justice delayed is justice denied," still retains its relevance 60 years later. This speech demonstrates the close connection between human spirituality and social justice. Also, in Finland, the policy of equality in the education system, free education and books for every child, is a spiritual expression of social justice

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